

Triterpenoids of Indian Dilleniaceae

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In consideration of previous work¹⁻⁴ and our taxonomic interest in the family Dilleniaceae we have examined the leaves of all the twelve indigenous species of Dilleniaceae⁵ with the aim of isolating and identifying the triterpenes and sterols. Table 1 summarizes our findings, which show that

$[\alpha]_D^{+43}$ (CHCl₃). β -sitosterol crystallised from methanol, m.p. 136-137°, $[\alpha]_D^{-35}$ (CHCl₃), acetate, m.p. 126-127°, $[\alpha]_D^{-35}$ (CHCl₃).

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TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM DILLENIACEAE SPECIES (PERCENTAGE YIELD/DRY WT).

Name of the species	betulinic acid	betulin	lupeol	β -sitosterol
<i>Acrotrema arnothianum</i> Wight	0.53	0.065	0.03	0.019
<i>Dillenia andamanica</i> Parkinson	0.50	0.082	0.02	0.015
<i>D. aurea</i> Smith	0.72	0.045	0.09	0.025
<i>D. bracteata</i> Wight	0.58	0.070	0.08	0.016
<i>D. indica</i> Linn	0.60	0.105	0.015	0.012
<i>D. pentagyna</i> Roxb.	0.98	0.150	0.01	0.010
<i>D. retusa</i> Thunb.	0.85	0.068	0.008	0.006
<i>D. scabralla</i> (D. Don) Roxb. exWall	0.575	0.120	0.032	0.022
<i>Tetracera akara</i> (Burm.f.) Merr.	1.05	0.045	0.045	0.005
<i>T. indica</i> (Houtt. ex Christm. & Panz., Merr.)	0.60	0.01	0.014	0.030
<i>T. sarmentosa</i> (L.) Vahl. subsp. andamanica (Hoogl.) Hoogl.	1.23	0.070	0.006	0.004
<i>T. scandens</i> (L.) Merr.	1.35	0.030	0.005	0.001

besides the widely distributed β -sitosterol, triterpenes of the lupene series viz., lupeol, betulin and butulinic acid occur in all the twelve species examined.

Experimental

Air dried and milled leaves were extracted with hot rectified spirit for 30 hrs. The semisolid mass obtained on evaporation of solvent was triturated exhaustively with ether. Ether insoluble residue being negligible was discarded. From ether soluble portion the triterpenes and sterol were isolated by chromatography over silica-gel and preparative tlc. The triterpenoids and sterol were identified by direct comparison with authentic samples⁶ (tlc, mmp, ir) and preparation of derivatives.

Betulinic acid crystallised from methanol, m.p. 306-309°, $[\alpha]_D^{+6}$ (Ethanol). On treatment with diazomethane methyl betulinate was obtained, crystallised from methanol, m.p. 222-224°. The methyl ester yielded acetate with pyridine-Ac₂O. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 198-201°, $[\alpha]_D^{+20}$ (CHCl₃). Betulin crystallised from benzene-methanol m.p. 252-254°, $[\alpha]_D^{+19}$ (CHCl₃). Acetate prepared, as above, crystallised from methanol, m.p. 220-224°, $[\alpha]_D^{+21}$ (CHCl₃). Lupeol crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 210-212°, $[\alpha]_D^{+22}$ (CHCl₃). Acetate crystallised from ethanol m.p. 209-212°,

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Chemical Examination of Essential Oil of *Lantana orangemene*

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The genus *Lantana* (Fam-Verbenaceae) has about 50 species mostly American, grown in tropical and sub-tropical regions¹. Only few species of *Lantana* are found to grow in Rohilkhand region of U. P. *Lantana orangemene* (flower orange) appears to be very much related to *Lantana camara*, botanically.

But the presence of *Lantana camara* proper in India is doubtful². The decoction of leaves is given in tetanus, malaria and rheumatism by the local people. Though few scientists have reported the chemistry of essential oil of *Lantana camara*^{3,4} and its varieties⁵, no work is available in literature on *Lantana orangemene*.

The essential oil from the leaves has been extracted by steam distillation in 0.2% yield. The pale yellow volatile oil was found to possess the following physico-chemical constants :

Specific gravity (0.88407), optical rotation (+2.212, ref. index (1.5492), acid value (1.874), ester value (26.98), carbonyl value (11.09%) and acetyl value (99.48).

Different constituents of the oil were separated by kiesel gel columns (10 × 4.5 cm) using the solvent benzene-ethylacetate (95 : 5). The separated fractions were tested for their purity on TLC (Plates-0.25 mm thick) and the isolated terpenes were identified by their ref. index, optical rotation, IR, NMR and co-TLC. IR measurements were made on Perkin-Elmer-457 infracord and NMR on Varian A-60D.

The isolated terpenes (%) are d-limonene (2.24), α -pinene (1.28), β -pinene (2.12), α -terpinene (1.80), β -caryophyllene (2.60), citral (4.04), 1,8-cineole (5.38), linalool (11.24), geraniol (18.64), α -terpeniol (3.44), menthol (8.24), dipentene (3.40) and β -phellandrene (21.92).

The presence of these constituents was also confirmed by GLC. The GLC was carried out in a gas chromatograph model-900B and other conditions were as follows :

Column-UCCW 982 10% 1.8 m

Temp. of column-100° 16 min
300° 4°/min.
250°

carrier gas-Nitrogen (30 ml/min)
Chart speed-5 mm/min.

Amount introduced-5 μ l

Detector-FID

The presence of β -phellandrene, d-limonene, β -pinene, α -terpinene and menthol are reported for the first time in the oil of *Lantana* genus. Difference in the chemical composition and physico-chemical constants of the oil obtained from the leaves of *Lantana orangemene* than that of *Lantana camara*⁸ clearly shows that both the plants are different.

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Chemical Investigations of *Anagallis arvensis* Flowers

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In furtherance of studies^{1,2}, the flowers of *Anagallis arvensis* have been found to contain three phyto-sterols (stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, α -spinasterol 3-glucoside) and three flavonoids (kaempferol, quercetin and rutin).

Experimental

Air dried flowers (275 g) of herb were Soxhleted with 95% ethanol. The greenish sticky residue (20%) after defatting with n-hexane, was triturated with petroleum ether 60-80° (Fraction I ; 15 mg).

The brown defatted residue on washing with absolute methanol left behind undissolved shining flakes (Fraction II ; 100 mg).

The solid mass, obtained on removal of methanol under vacuum, was triturated with ether (Fraction III ; 50 mg) leaving undissolved residue (Fraction IV).

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